

The founder of the investment management firm, [Shaye Hirsch](#) was born in Brooklyn, New York in 1974. He attended the Yeshiva Torah Temimah followed by Yeshivas Toras Moshe in Jerusalem, Israel, from 1991 to 1992. At 1996, Hirsch [graduated from the Touro College](#), a private college of higher and professional education.

Shaye Hirsch spent the first 10 years of his professional career working for a full-service Securities Firm. There he quickly excelled to the position CEO.

In 2006, the [experienced hedge fund manager](#), who has passion for investing, commitment to delivering excellent risk-adjusted returns, and love of entrepreneurship, founded Brio Capital Management. This investment management firm has the goal to maximize the total return by incorporating a variety of strategies. Shaye Hirsch, as the firm's hedge fund manager employs an opportunistic and event-driven investment approach. Shaye dedicates himself to providing exceptional investment management services by incorporating its specialized investment strategies, and disciplined management to capture opportunity while minimizing risk.

Over the course of his career, Hirsch gained skills which include, but are not limited to: Equity Investments and trading, Fixed-Income and Derivative Trading, Portfolio Management, and Investment Banking and Risk Management.